

Resilience Amidst Devastation: Qualitative Insights from Gaza During the War

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ABSTRACT

This case study explores the lived experiences of Palestinians in Gaza amidst the ongoing War that started on October 7th, 2023. Drawing on the detailed testimony of one of the co-authors and his observations, the paper highlights the profound socioeconomic, social, and psychological impacts of the War on Gaza's population.

The case describes the daily strategies individuals and families employ to survive and adapt, taking the unique economics of the Gaza war. It provides a nuanced understanding of resilience values in the face of extreme adversity. The findings underscore the need for comprehensive humanitarian aid, targeted economic and socioeconomic driven intervention programs that would alleviate the suffering and promote sustainable recovery in Gaza.

Keywords: War on Gaza, War Economics, Socioeconomic Impact, Resilience, Coping Mechanisms, Personal Testimonies, Lived Experiences

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1. INTRODUCTION

This paper reviews personal observations as a case study that describes the socioeconomic conditions in Gaza, which are exacerbated by a prolonged blockade and recurrent conflicts. The total strip poverty and unemployment, coupled with extreme restrictions on movement and trade, have created a humanitarian crisis of unprecedented scale as a consequence of the War on Gaza on October 7, 2023. Since the escalation of the War led to widespread destruction and displacement of the Palestinians in the Gaza Strip, the authors provide insights based on the capture of the real-life experiences of Gazans during the first eight months.

The study explores the field coping mechanisms and the role of the 'Social Capital' in maintaining the collective wealth of Gaza. Buheji and Hasan (2024).

2. CASE STUDY

Testimony Dated: June 3, 2024, by Professor Mohammed Migdad

2.1. Situation of Gaza Before October 7th, 2023

The Palestinians in Gaza have nothing left to lose. According to UNRWA statistics from August 2023, the poverty rate has exceeded 80%, and the rate of extreme poverty, including food insecurity, has reached 60%. This is the result of an economic blockade that is among the harshest in the world, specifically targeting Palestine and especially the Gaza Strip. The blockade is comprehensive: economic, financial, and restrictions on movement and trade, including travel for medical treatment or tourism.

The economic and trade blockade has severely restricted the Palestinians' ability to import and export freely. Import and export activities depend entirely on Israeli approvals, which impose hundreds of restrictions. Under the pretext of dual-use, these restrictions have largely prevented the import of goods essential for industry, agriculture, and fishing, as well as the construction sector. This includes construction materials like iron, cement, pipes, internet cables, and raw materials necessary for industry, such as fertilizers and agricultural medicines.

The financial blockade has tightened restrictions on banks and financial institutions, preventing many Palestinian banks from engaging in international transactions. Additionally, the Israeli occupation has denied the Palestinian Authority the right to issue its own currency, perpetuating liquidity problems, a shortage of small change, and foreign exchange issues. These financial difficulties particularly afflict Palestinians in Gaza, especially during holidays, Ramadan, the start of the school year, and other significant times.

Regarding movement and travel for purposes such as medical treatment, trade, or tourism, the Israeli occupation has severely restricted these activities, particularly for Gazans. Gazans have faced varying degrees of difficulty in travelling, sometimes being entirely unable to travel for months. When travel is permitted, individuals often wait for many months for their turn, paying thousands of dollars for travel permits. The cost for a person and their family to travel can reach up to \$50,000. Tens of thousands of Palestinians are entirely banned from travelling, not only through the Erez crossing but also through the Salah al-Din gate between Gaza and Egypt.

The restrictions on travel extend to patients needing treatment abroad, with frequent Israeli refusals and constraints leading to the indirect killing of patients due to the lack of appropriate treatments and medical equipment, especially for cancer and chronic diseases. The suffering extends beyond economic and movement restrictions to direct violence, including shootings and bombings of homes and civilians. Thousands of Palestinians were killed before October 7, 2023. This is in addition to the policies of humiliation and domination practised by the Israeli occupation against Palestinians and their leadership.

Continuous assaults on Palestinians in Jerusalem, Al-Aqsa Mosque, and throughout the West Bank have made life in these areas nearly impossible. Palestinians in these regions face severe difficulties moving from one place to another due to the fragmentation of areas in Jerusalem and the West Bank.

Given all this, coupled with Palestinians' frustration with any political solution and Israel's procrastination and outright rejection of the two-state solution, as declared by many Israeli officials, the events of October 7, 2023, emerged as a significant initiative by the Palestinians as a result of all that mentioned.

2.2. The sudden attack known as "Al-Aqsa Flood" on October 7, 2023

This date marked the beginning of the genocide named by Hamas as Al-Aqsa Flood. This operation commenced with a coordinated and unexpected attack launched by Hamas against Israel on the morning of Saturday, corresponding to (22 Rabi' al-Awwal 1445 AH), in response to ongoing Israeli aggressions against the Palestinian people.

Thousands of rockets were fired from the Gaza Strip, governed by Hamas, towards Israel. Additionally, thousands of armed Palestinians entered the border areas adjacent to Gaza, known as the Gaza Envelope, and other nearby towns, where they took control of several military sites, especially in Sderot, Ofakim, and Netivot. Fierce clashes ensued in these settlements and others, resulting in the capture of numerous soldiers and civilians who were taken to Gaza. The attackers also seized a number of Israeli military vehicles. The attack led to the deaths of approximately 1,500 Israelis at the start of the battle and the capture of around 250 more, according to Israeli press reports.

Not only did armed militants from Palestinian factions enter the Gaza envelope, but thousands of civilians also crossed in various ways after the militants opened the borders. We saw civilians taking belongings from these towns, believing that these are Palestinian lands occupied by Israel and that everything in them rightfully belongs to Palestinians.

The attack caught the Israeli government, military, and intelligence agencies unexpectedly, despite confirmed warnings from Egyptian and Saudi intelligence to their Israeli counterparts, which were not taken seriously at all. Saudi Arabia linked its warning to an imminent explosion in Palestinian territories due to ongoing occupation and the lack of political prospects. Egyptian intelligence warned of a disaster unless political progress was made, and the King of Jordan expressed regret that Palestinians have no civil rights or freedom of movement.

The sudden attack was due to Hamas and its military wing, Al-Qassam Brigades, employing precise and deceptive tactics, making any movements appear merely as training exercises. Additionally, Hamas repeatedly indicated that it was focused on governance, internal politics, and creating job opportunities, especially within the occupied territories. Their lack of retaliation for the assassination of leaders from the Islamic Jihad also portrayed them as resigned to the status quo, seeking economic solutions to the crises in Gaza, which is governed by Hamas and suffering hardships in every sector due to the Israeli blockade and the severe exploitation by the Sons of Sinai Company, which drains Gaza of liquidity and continues to impoverish it blatantly and unjustly.

2.3. The Unexpected War

Despite around 44 countries condemning Hamas's attack on the Gaza border towns, the severity and intensity of the Israeli response—targeting everything in Gaza, from buildings to trees, children, and women—has led to a dramatic increase in casualties. According to Ma'an News Agency, the number of martyrs has risen to 36,439, with 82,627 injured and 10,000 missing under the rubble since October 7th. This level of killing and destruction has led most of the world to condemn the Israeli attacks on civilians. Many now suspect that this war was planned, regardless of the October 7 attack, with the aim of either forcibly or voluntarily relocating Palestinians under the pretext of eliminating Hamas. There is substantial evidence supporting this view.

The "Sword of the Prophet" war—according to Israeli terminology—began on the same day as the flood and has continued for about eight months, causing extensive death and destruction. Israel has firmly rejected all calls for a ceasefire and prisoner exchange deals, despite American and international proposals and Hamas's willingness to consider them.

2.4. The Situation in Gaza After Eight Months from October 7th , 2023 War on Gaza

Rather than discussing the history of this war, I want to focus on its various impacts on the people of Gaza. I will attempt to address the real experiences faced by Gazans.

2.4.1. Description of the Closely Observed Economic Conditions During the War

How can we discuss an economy that has been ravaged by a blockade for twenty years, recurring wars every two years, and then a brutal war in October 2023 that destroyed everything, leaving no people or property intact? We are talking about an economy that has been wounded and diminished by the loss of 130,000 human resources, representing about 6% of the population in a very small area of about 360 square kilometres.

Before October 7, poverty rates exceeded 80%, with food insecurity over 60%, and unemployment similarly high. After the war, life became almost nonexistent, with all residents displaced either within the governorates, between governorates, or emigrating abroad.

Factories, farms, shops, infrastructure, roads, bridges, internet and communication networks, electricity, water, and even sewage systems have been destroyed. Commercial life has completely ceased, and borders have been closed except for aid entry. People have become reliant on aid, if available. The educational and health systems have also been completely destroyed, with schools and hospitals demolished and scientists and doctors killed in Gaza.

People fled their homes under bombardment and could not carry their belongings, leaving them in need of everything. They took whatever cash they had (if any), which ran out over the eight months of the war. Most salaries ceased, replaced by sporadic and minimal loans, if available. Many relied on intermittent aid, often sold at high prices in markets.

Most people have lived in tents, as buildings were destroyed, and the remaining structures were rented at exorbitant prices. In the tents, there is no water, gas, or electricity—cooking is done on wood fires, and water is fetched with buckets. Fuel is scarce, with a kilogram of cooking gas costing 100 shekels and a litre of gasoline over 25 dollars.

Figure (1) Photo of the Gaza Displaced Memoir Author while trying to collect his observations in his family tent

2.4.2. The Special Economics of the Gaza War

In traditional wars, war economics is defined as "a set of emergency measures taken by modern states to mobilize their economies for production during wartime." Philippe Le Billon describes war economics as "the system of resource production, mobilization, and allocation to support the war effort," including:

- Increasing tax rates
- Implementing resource allocation programs
- Enhancing planning and intervention during the war
- Recruitment for civilian purposes, such as women's land armies
- The "Bevin Boys" in the UK during World War II.

An economist, Seymour Melman (2003) notes that "the profligate nature of much military spending can ultimately harm technological progress." In the case of civil wars, war economics is defined as "the continuation of the economy by other means."

According to the Berghof Research Center (2005), what characterizes war economics in civil wars, where the government and rebels are the conflicting parties, is the manipulation and destruction of the formal economy, transforming it into a black market and informal economy. This involves policies of looting, extortion, and violence against civilians to gain control over valuable assets and labour independence. In such decentralized economies, reliance on smuggling and exploitation of minority populations thrives.

Much of what has been written about war economics in general or civil wars specifically does not exactly apply to the situation in Gaza for several reasons:

1. Gaza was not an independent state before the war.
2. Gaza was financially and economically blockaded.
3. The Gaza government does not fully govern Gaza; instead, it shares control with UNRWA, Egypt, Israel, and the Ramallah government more than it controls Gaza itself.
4. Therefore, the Gaza government lacks governance and economic tools.

Nevertheless, the Gaza government has attempted to implement some necessary measures during the war economy, such as:

1. The police coordinated with UNRWA to protect the entry of aid to ensure it did not negatively impact either side, despite the Israeli occupation's rejection of any attempts to regulate aid flow.
2. It organized imports and directed them to the most essential goods for citizens' survival amid Israeli restrictions on the number of incoming trucks.
3. Efforts were made to provide diesel fuel through various means for police vehicles and institutions serving citizens, especially civil defence, emergency services, and overall health.
4. The government managed to secure funding to continue operations by utilizing revenue from smuggled cigarettes.
5. It attempted to coordinate with the Egyptian side to increase the number of trucks entering Gaza.
6. It worked on organizing the sale and distribution of imports by establishing a point-of-sale system adhering to government pricing.
7. It imposed revolutionary sanctions on monopolistic traders or thieves threatening social peace.

Despite these efforts, commodity prices remained extremely high, with the system nearly absent, security weak, and shortages severe enough to cause famine in Gaza City and the northern areas, with a 25-kilogram bag of flour reaching nearly \$1,000. All of this happened due to Israeli policies aimed at spreading chaos to expedite the end of Hamas's rule. Consequently, the Israeli side targeted any entities working on organizing, protecting security and peace, and managing aid distribution. Many Palestinian police units securing aid convoys from UNRWA were repeatedly bombarded.

All these factors led to the collapse of the economic situation, the deterioration of all sectors, and the loss of job opportunities after eight months of genocide. It also resulted in the entire population relying on aid, which did not reach everyone fairly and was often stolen and sold in markets to displaced individuals who ran out of money over time. This has led to widespread impoverishment, with many living below the poverty line and facing severe food insecurity.

2.4.3. Opportunities that came as a result of the War Economics

Inspiration economy teaches us that we can explore opportunities during challenges, Buheji (2016). A resilience economy also teaches us that we can discover stronger agile resilience once we start absorbing shock. The war on Gaza created a need that had to be fulfilled with non-traditional jobs that did not exist. Also, the displaced individuals had to bring money to meet basic living expenses.

Gazan had to bring a variety of types of sources of income that generated minimal sources of life dignity and did not require great funds; these can be summarised in the following areas:

- **Street Vending:** Selling goods on makeshift stalls, which often included aid items—either stolen or excess supplies that citizens had—and some goods purchased from traders.
- **Fruit and Vegetable Stalls:** Temporary stalls selling produce, depending on availability, which often halted and rarely provided sufficient income for survival.
- **Selling Arabic Tobacco:** With cigarette prices reaching 140 shekels each (approximately \$35), some started vending rolled Arabic tobacco.
- **Tent and Shelter Installation:** Setting up tents, shelters, and creating bathrooms, including digging wells, was crucial for displaced people living in tents. This work was challenging due to a shortage of digging tools and materials for building bathrooms, such as wood and tarpaulins.
- **Queue Work:** Individuals worked by standing in queues for others. For example, they would queue at bakeries to buy bread and resell it for a profit or queue for egg cartons or similar items.
- **ATM Queue Jobs:** With cash shortages and bank closures, people stood in line at ATMs, sometimes waiting a day or more to withdraw 1,000 shekels. Some individuals paid 50 shekels (about \$13) for a place in line.
- **Aid Truck Theft:** Gangs, often from large families living in marginalized areas, engaged in stealing aid trucks.
- **Expansion of Black Market Trade:** Traditional businesses declined while war profiteers and black market traders expanded their operations.
- **Basic Cafés:** Establishments providing coffee, internet, and a place to sit became popular among those in need.
- **Innovative Transportation:** With fuel shortages, goods and people were transported by horse-drawn carts or donkeys. Cars were modified to use cooking oil as fuel, with trailers added to increase capacity.
- **Individual Ventures:** Numerous personal ventures emerged, such as currency exchange and money transfer services, with commission rates exceeding 20%.

2.4.4. The Observations on Land-, Air-, and Sea-Aid Supply

Before the genocide, Gaza was heavily reliant on aid, with about 70% of the population receiving assistance. This dependency continued and became more widespread after the genocide, affecting nearly all residents of Gaza as displacement led to universal need and poverty.

The UN Relief and Works Agency (UNRWA) and some international organizations have been delivering hundreds of truckloads of aid daily. However, these efforts were hampered by poor organization and coordination between aid-providing entities and security forces, leading to theft and black-market sales of much of the aid.

Aid enters through the Salah al-Din, Karam Abu Salem, and Israeli Karni crossings. Due to Israeli restrictions and the congestion of hundreds of trucks on the Egyptian side, which are unable to enter and result in spoilage of much of the aid, some countries have started relying on air transport to deliver it.

- **Food Supply through AirDrop**

Several countries, including Egypt, Jordan, the UAE, and some European nations, devised methods to drop aid by air to the besieged areas. Although this provided some necessary materials, there were several issues:

1. The quantities were minimal and distributed in a chaotic manner.
2. This led to several disasters among waiting civilians, such as the flour massacre at the Nitsarim checkpoint, where aid often landed around tank positions.
3. In many cases, parachutes for aid packages did not open, causing packages to fall on homes and people, partially destroying some buildings and causing fatalities.
4. Air transport cost was significantly higher than land transport via the Salah al-Din crossing between Egypt and Palestine.
5. It is crucial to ensure that Egyptian and Palestinian authorities solely manage the Salah al-Din and Karam Abu Salem crossings without interference or restrictions imposed by the occupation forces.

- **Food Supply through Sea Dock**

The American floating pier, which became a topic of significant debate, was built at the Nitsarim crossing. There was controversy over whether it was intended to seize Gaza's gas, facilitate the voluntary relocation of Gazans to relieve pressure on Egypt, or simply bring in aid. According to Channel 12, Washington is considering using helicopters to deliver aid to Gaza after the floating pier, which cost \$320 million, failed.

The debate also surrounded the ownership and management of the pier—whether it was American, Israeli, or would eventually become Palestinian once the genocide ended. The pier was poorly constructed, and even minor winds and waves caused parts of it to scatter, leading to its temporary relocation to the Israeli pier of Ashdod for repairs. Despite these issues, some aid was delivered to Gaza through this port.

Overall, it can be said that the Egyptian-Palestinian crossing could have been sufficient for aid delivery if Egypt had utilized its sovereignty over the crossing to allow all aid to enter without delays that lead to spoilage, without considering Israeli attempts to obstruct and prevent aid.

- **The Constraints on UNRWA and its Role**

UNRWA is the primary international institution dedicated to the relief and employment of Palestinian refugees in Palestine and the diaspora. Its existence is seen as politically linked to the Palestinian issue and will persist as long as there are Palestinian refugees. Consequently, Israel views UNRWA with suspicion, distrust, and sometimes hostility.

During this genocide, there was an Israeli push to marginalize or even eliminate UNRWA's role, replacing it with the roles of other international organizations. UNRWA and the Palestinian government, both in Gaza and the West Bank rejected this move. Therefore, it is essential to strengthen UNRWA's role and reject alternative roles for any other international organization. UNRWA should continue to be a supporting and complementary entity rather than a replacement.

2.5. Memoir of Resilience Economics Approaches During the First Eight Months of War on Gaza

2.5.1. The Weavers – Al-Miqdad Family and Their Displaced Persons

The genocide that started on October 7th, 2023 caused hundreds of thousands of Palestinian families to flee from northern Gaza to the south. Our home in Rafah became a refuge for about 100 displaced people, while the family house in Rafah sheltered over 300 displaced individuals.

As days passed, children and women began to feel boredom and fear, having exhausted traditional games like cards, chess, Monopoly, hopscotch, and hide and seek. With winter approaching, the need for woollen garments became evident. They proposed the idea of knitting wool to create pieces that would keep them warm, and so it began.

My granddaughter Layan had previously tried to learn knitting but struggled due to a lack of patience and alternative ways to spend her time. However, with the absence of alternatives during the war, she gave it another try. To her surprise, she succeeded and produced many pieces, becoming a serious competitor to her grandmother in both the speed and quality of woollen knitting. Some of the woollen items she made were even shipped across borders to the USA, Turkey, and other places, proving that this idea could be developed into a profitable economic activity for the family and its workers. The home became a knitting workshop managed by the grandmother, with her daughters, granddaughters, and some displaced individuals working together as a beehive of activity, creating woollen products like scarves, hats, gloves, and wallets.

2.5.2. Stalls and New Traders

While the previous examples focused on women and girls, the boys turned to trading. They learned the basics of commerce and became small business owners. Some sold vegetables, others biscuits, some specialized in selling traditional sweets, and others set up stalls with various food and canned goods. These activities positively affected the children, refining their knowledge and shaping their personalities. They also contributed to supporting their families, and gaining valuable skills and life experiences.

I was personally surprised by the children's talents in managing their businesses and their ability to keep up with the market and interact with customers, even though the oldest of them was only 14 years old. They experienced both success and failure, adapting their business areas based on their results, making it a pioneering experience and practical education in trade and business.

2.5.3. Al-Miqdad Bakery for Pastries and Baked Goods:

Upon relocating to Rafah with my family, I noticed that my brothers were sitting idly at home, avoiding work due to fear of the war, despite being business owners in furniture carpentry. I decided to encourage them to overcome their fear and engage in trade.

My brother Al-Miqdad began with various activities, such as selling falafel, vegetables, and canned goods. Some of these ventures succeeded, while others did not. However, with numerous attempts, he stabilised his business, especially in the trading sector. He bought large quantities of supplies from relief centers and sold them wholesale to traders, which helped him cover a significant portion of his debts and support his family.

My brother Nabil chose to sell pastries and sweets. He and his family started producing and selling pastries in small quantities due to the scarcity of essential ingredients. Over time, as ingredients became available but remained expensive, he expanded the project, turning it into a source of livelihood for over 20 family members and experienced displaced persons in baking. He invested in improving the bakery's tools and equipment and is now preparing for new developments for Ramadan.

The bakery project has been very successful and may continue post-war, potentially leading Nabil to shift his profession from carpentry to pastry making.

2.5.4. Layan's Clothing Store

My son has a clothing store in Nuseirat, opposite the Al-Qassam Mosque, with clothes worth more than \$120,000, belonging to around 20 partners in the company. After we moved to Rafah and with my son's concerns about the store being targeted in an airstrike, I suggested relocating the store to Rafah. He supported the idea, and we decided to move the store.

The relocation and sale of the clothes turned out to be a very beneficial experience, with numerous advantages:

- a- Saving the family's and partners' money from potential destruction, thank God.
- b- My family members gained experience in sales and working in the store. They learned the sales techniques and how to interact with customers.
- c- Distributing some of the store's clothes to the displaced as part of charitable efforts. We managed to secure some external funding to help the poor and needy among the displaced with clothing, as they fled their homes without any belongings, increasing their need for everything.
- d- It became a source of income for the family during the war, especially since I, as a university professor, had not received a salary for more than nine months, making our financial situation difficult without this trade and the sale of clothes.
- e- Working at the clothing store opened up new business opportunities for me, providing real financial benefits for my family and supplying the camp with necessary goods. I traded in flour, soda, foodstuffs, and clothes imported from Egypt.
- f- Personally, managing the store kept me busy, relieving me of boredom, fear, and thoughts of the war's horrors.
- g- We were able to return the partners' and shareholders' money despite the destructive war.

2.5.5. Al-Miqdad Charitable Kitchen

A charitable kitchen is a place where food is prepared with charitable, self, or joint funding and distributed to the needy for free. There are many generous people willing to donate and feed others, but the challenge lies in finding a mediator who can transform their money into charitable work. Therefore, we contacted several philanthropists, some of whom were ready to support displaced families financially or through food parcels or meals. This led to the idea of establishing Al-Miqdad Charitable Kitchen.

Al-Miqdad Charitable Kitchen began operating, providing meals intermittently depending on the available support and funding. The kitchen faced many challenges due to the siege on Gaza, the fierce war, and the scarcity of basic food supplies. We did not limit our contacts to philanthropists only; we also reached out to foreign organizations like WCK and UNRWA. We agreed to establish a full kitchen capable of feeding 500 displaced families (about 2000 people, mostly displaced). We donated a private space to set up the kitchen, a 400 square meter barracks owned by the family.

Establishing the kitchen had numerous benefits for everyone:

- 22 unemployed individuals were employed on a temporary basis under UNRWA's official employment, all of whom were in need, mostly from family, relatives, and women.

- Providing a daily meal for all displaced family members, neighbours, and the needy, alleviating their living burden.

- Providing an intermittent dinner meal depending on the availability of food supplies.

The WCK organization provided us with all necessary kitchen equipment, including large pots, wood-burning stoves, and bread ovens. They also supplied us with quantities of food, fuel, water, solar panels, and more.

2.5.6. The General Trade Experience

The exorbitant inflation and sky-high prices that swept the markets drove everyone to seek money, prompting anyone who could engage in trade. We managed to open a commercial store to trade in various goods as they became available. We dealt with imported clothes from Egypt, various juices, flour, vegetables, bread, chicken, meat, and more.

We faced a significant issue with extremely high prices. A major factor was the steep transportation costs in Egypt through the Sinai Trading Company. Additionally, unethical monopolistic practices by some traders exacerbated the problem. The Israeli occupation allowed only five companies to handle imports, reinforcing monopolies and creating unprecedented price hikes. The occupation's restrictions on most goods further worsened the situation.

2.6. Collection of the Personal Experiences Last Eight Months Since War on Gaza Started

During these eight months of the war on Gaza, I have experienced the remarkable resilience of the people of Gaza in adapting to the most challenging conditions. This resilience is about surviving and creating an environment conducive to business that allows them to cover living expenses. This was evident in the actions of mothers, daughters, sons, and especially the head of the family, who tried every means to facilitate living conditions, innovate ways to secure a livelihood, and remain steadfast on Palestinian land in Gaza, resisting both voluntary and forced displacement despite the harsh circumstances and difficulties of life.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1. The Economics of the War

The economics of war involves the study of the economic impacts of conflict on a specific nation, community or region, and/or on the global economy. It encompasses a wide range of issues, including the costs of military expenditure, the effects on GDP, resource allocation, labor markets, and the broader socioeconomic consequences. Ballentine and Nitzschke (2005)

Besides military spending during wartime, these expenditures often increase significantly, diverting resources from other areas of the economy. However, the most important part of the economics of the war for the scope of this paper is the economic disruption caused. It focuses on areas around survival, starting with looking for or supplying food in strips during times of scarcity. Hassoun et. al. (2024).

War can lead to the displacement of populations, causing disruptions in labour markets and increasing the burden on social services in host areas. Wars also destroy physical infrastructure, such as roads, bridges, and factories, which can hinder economic activity. Besides, war can disrupt trade routes and lead to economic sanctions, affecting both the warring nations and their trading partners. Meisels (2011).

War often exacerbates economic inequality, with certain groups bearing the brunt of the conflict's economic consequences, Melman (2003). Besides, the impact on health services and education systems can have long-lasting effects on human capital development. Others argue that war leads to inefficiencies and a misallocation of resources, ultimately harming economic growth. This is why Hedges (2002) sees that wars give us other meanings for life.

3.2. The Importance of Learning from the Personal Memoir of the War

Learning from personal moments (or "memoirs") during the war helps to bring unique insights into the human aspects of conflict that broader historical analyses may overlook.

It shows that dealing with loss-coping with a yearning for lost livelihood is not the only thing we should see from the war on Gaza. Buheji (2024a)

There are several key reasons why a personal memoir is important. The first thing that comes to mind is that personal stories help humanize war's abstract and often overwhelming statistics, fostering empathy and understanding among those who read or hear them. These difficult time moments reveal the complexity and diversity of individual experiences, showing that war affects people in myriad ways beyond the battlefield. Buheji et al. (2024)

These memoirs give historical accuracy and eyewitness accounts of the war detail. Personal narratives provide firsthand accounts that can verify, challenge, or enrich official records and historical analyses. These stories often include cultural and social contexts that might be missing from formal histories, offering a fuller picture of the times. The daily observations bring more perspective into the psychological insights of the people living in the war and how its impact is creating for them PTSD, grief, and resilience. Besides, these personal accounts can reveal the motivations behind individuals' actions during the war and the factors that influenced their morale and decision-making. Al-Muhannadi and Buheji (2024).

Case studies based on war witness memoirs also bring educational value, as personal stories can engage students and the public more effectively than abstract accounts, making studying history more relatable and impactful. This encourages critical thinking, as learners must consider multiple perspectives and the reliability of different sources. Besides, it emphasises the human experience of finding reasons to live and survive. Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2024a)

The personal stories can be powerful tools for advocacy, highlighting the need for humanitarian aid, veterans' support, and conflict prevention measures. It gives clarity to the reasons to live and continue resisting. The stories show how Gazans overcome feelings of betrayal and let down by the world by extending their capacity for survival in Gaza. Buheji (2024b), "Restrepo" Documentary (2010), McNamara (2003).

Personal moments of war have inspired countless works of literature, art, and film, contributing to cultural heritage and collective memory, Frank (1947). Besides, as Buheji and Khunji (2023) mentioned, sharing personal stories can be a form of healing for survivors and a way to preserve their legacy and rehabilitate themselves.

Documents such as Anne Frank's (1947) diary, which has been published in 67 languages, provide an example of the intimate insights that come from individuals' daily lives and struggles during wartime.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a qualitative approach, utilizing the depth of the observations collected by one of the authors to gather firsthand accounts from residents of Gaza. The testimony provides a rich, detailed narrative of life under siege and suffering from the atrocities of the war. The methodology emphasizes the importance of capturing the voices of those directly affected, ensuring that their experiences and perspectives are at the forefront of future research.

5. FINDINGS

Learning from the personal moments of the war on Gaza is crucial for understanding its full impact as it provides depth and nuance to historical events, fosters empathy and critical thinking, and can inform better policies and advocacy efforts. By preserving and studying the personal narratives of this case study, we can better appreciate the experiences of those who lived through war and ensure that their lessons are not forgotten. The findings reveal a complex web of challenges faced by Gazans, including economic hardship, displacement, and psychological trauma.

The memoir shows that the blockade and recurrent wars have raised the capacity of the Gazans to demonstrate remarkable resilience by engaging in informal economic activities, such as street vending, black market trade, and innovative small-scale enterprises, Buheji and Mushimiyimana (2023b). These adaptive strategies highlight the community's resourcefulness and underscore the need for formal economic opportunities and support. Al-Muhannadi and Buheji (2024)

The author of the memoir saw that if the war continued, human greed and crime would increase, similar to what Kurtenbach and Rettberg (2018) mentioned in their studies of wars during and aftermath.

As the case shows for a sample of how a family survives daily, social networks and community solidarity have played a crucial role in helping individuals and families cope with hardships. Informal support systems have been vital for survival, including shared resources and communal efforts like establishing charitable kitchens and informal markets.

Despite the prolonged exposure to violence and insecurity that led to widespread psychological distress, particularly among children and adolescents, community-driven initiatives, such as collective activities and cultural preservation efforts, have provided some relief and a sense of normalcy.

The case emphasizes the resilience and adaptability of Gaza's population in the face of extreme adversity. The detailed testimonies provide valuable insights into the lived realities of conflict and blockade, offering a humanized perspective often missing in broader political and economic analyses.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Understanding the economics of war involves analyzing both immediate and long-term impacts on various facets of the economy, requiring a comprehensive approach that considers direct costs, opportunity costs, and broader socioeconomic consequences.

This paper analyse the qualitative memoir that provides a profound and detailed examination of the lived experiences of Palestinians in Gaza amid the ongoing conflict that began on October 7th, 2023. By drawing on firsthand testimony and field collective observations, the study sheds light on the severe socioeconomic, social, and psychological impacts of the war on Gaza's population.

The findings highlight the extraordinary resilience and adaptability of individuals and families who have developed diverse strategies to survive and cope with the hardships imposed by the war and blockade. These adaptive mechanisms, including informal economic activities and community solidarity, underscore the resourcefulness of Gazans but also emphasize the urgent need for comprehensive humanitarian aid, targeted economic support, and international policy interventions.

This paper implies that the detailed narratives captured in this study not only enrich our understanding of the human dimension of Gaza during the war, but also serve to ensure that these personal experiences are recognized and addressed in promoting sustainable recovery and alleviating the ongoing suffering in Gaza. More work is recommended in this line.

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